

EMERGING NEED OF ENGLISH LANGUAGE IN TOURISM INDUSTRY: NEW ERA 21ST CENTURY

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Cite This Article: Asha Krishnan & Thomas Mathew, "Emerging Need of English Language in Tourism Industry: New Era 21st Century", International Journal of Interdisciplinary Research in Arts and Humanities, Volume 8, Issue 1, Page Number 54-57, 2023.

Abstract:

In tourist industry English language have become very important in all geographical locations to reach practically all countries of the globe, becoming for many of them an important economic sector in terms of income generation, foreign exchange earnings and employment creation. This study mainly focus to determine the emerging need of English language in tourist industry. The data has been collected from 100 respondents and they are analysed using simple percentage test and chi-square test. The study concludes that English plays a dominant part in nearly all the fields in the present globalized world, there's a need to bandy its part in sightseer assiduity.

Key Words: Tourist, Industry, English, Geographical, Globalization, New Era, etc.,

Introduction:

Tourism operation is a system of planning, organizing, controlling and leading to negotiate the tourism organizational thing similar as the satisfaction, the effectiveness of delivering the requirements, wants and prospects of the transnational excursionists. Luchien defined tourism organizational operation as ideas containing rudiments of operation approach predicated in a value base, and equipped with language. English Language is seen as being common to the association community, as a social resource, to social media, and having a common language makes it easier to communicate functional moxie. It's used to transfer knowledge. Fair and enforceable programs can help empower workers by furnishing them with freedom. Programs, when drafted duly, can help in organizational operation and cost savings, plus reduce time- consuming problems. Michael Porter (2003) refocused out that the Thai tourism assiduity was transnational competitive in tourism request, still the collaboration across the assiduity was weak. To ameliorate the collaboration, the Ministry of Tourism and Sports need to have further focus on technology and clear policy for organizational operation. It'll encourage further information collaboration. The fast worldwide progression of tourism operation has been a significant advance within a tourism assiduity over the rearmost decades¹ Communication is essential to the operation English language will be an 2 important means to communicate within tourism associations and for tourism operation Language also activates the tourism association to drive forward. 3 Buckley et al refocused out that the language plays part in easing communication between head quarter and accessories. Accordingly, high- position labor force with language chops are getting more and more necessary to commercial effectiveness and success in tourism operation in the global 4 terrain. Labor force with language chops are demanded as original agents of tourism association doing domestic stint business. Effective tourism operation is concluded that it's dependent incompletely on the use of language, especially in the form of creation, instructions and other written material.

Tourism can play a significant part in sustainable development and the United Nations Environment Programme (UNEP) and the World Tourism Organization (WTO) wish to encourage all countries to make sure that their programs and conduct for its development and operation completely embrace the principles of sustainability. Likewise, programs to promote sustainable development should take full account of the openings offered by tourism. Colorful transnational conventions and affirmations have put forward principles and guidelines for sustainable tourism and the significance of tourism and its sustainability was underscored at the World Summit on Sustainable Development. Numerous countries declare that they're pursuing, or wish to pursue, programs for 'sustainable tourism '. In recent period, utmost governments, transnational development agencies, trade associations, academic institutions and non-governmental associations admit that, without sustainability, there cannot be development that generates benefits to all stakeholders, solves serious and critical problems similar as extreme poverty, and preserves the precious natural and man- made coffers on which mortal substance is grounded. The tourism sector couldn't remain indifferent to the sustainability challenge of our times. This is why the World Tourism Organization (WTO) focuses its premonitory and specialized backing services on programs, development guidelines, operation ways and dimension instruments that allow public and original governments, as well as the tourism assiduity, to incorporate sustainability principles into their decision making process and day- to- day operations. Tourism is in a veritably special position to profit original communities, economically and socially, and to raise mindfulness and support for conservation of the terrain. Within the tourism sector, profitable development and environmental protection shouldn't be seen as opposing forces they should be pursued hand in hand as bourns that can and should be mutually buttressing. Programs and conduct must aim to strengthen the benefits and reduce the costs of tourism. Big issues are at stake then.

Farther massive growth is prognosticated for tourism between now and 2020, furnishing excellent openings for spreading substance but presenting considerable challenges and implicit pitfalls to the terrain and original communities if not well managed. Climate change is honored as a major global issue, with significant counter accusations for tourism.

Review of Literature:

Sethi, 2019 analyzed this destination in an in-depth study on the existing impact of tourism activities in the Lahaul-Pangi region of Himachal Pradesh, with particular emphasis on nature tourism and adventure tourism. The study analyzed the different impacts of tourism on these places and thus developed a set of recommendations to ensure the establishment of sustainable tourism. Recommendations from the study include installing signs to inform visitors of precautions, documenting routes and important points of interest, inclusion of local tourist offices for better tourist services, building regulations of hotels and bed and breakfasts, capacity building of local communities, formal training of local guides and certification, by restricting tourist access to protected and vulnerable areas, strengthening waste management systems, improving social media outreach programs, and creating unions and associations to better enforce these programs. All of these recommendations can lead to better implementation of sustainable tourism, building local communities and better use of a destination's natural resources, ensuring that the negative impacts of tourism are kept to a minimum.

Singh and Ganguly, 2020 a study on Sustainable Tourism Policy for Environment and People of Himachal Pradesh, Guiding Principles, Mission Statement and Goals for Sustainable Tourism Development in India Himachal Pradesh are widely articulated. The Sustainable Tourism Development Policy adopts various guiding principles such as Atithi Devo Bhava, Inclusive Tourism and Sustainable Tourism to shape the future of tourism in Himachal Pradesh. The various objectives of the policy include "to provide exceptional tourism, accessible and free for all", "to emphasize employment and socio-economic development through tourism", "to ensure the coherence of the experience tourism" and "encouraging the private sector" and investment." Recommendations from the study include strict adherence to sustainable tourism development policies and ensuring continuous policy improvement and achievement of all policy goals.

Kumar & Shekhar, 2020 A survey of technologies and innovations shaping the future of rural tourism in India According to researchers, rural tourism is directly linked to the development of sustainable tourism because the ecology of a rural destination is very fragile and even the most small tourist activity can destroy the entire ecology of this rural destination if not managed properly. The researchers found significant research gaps on how the identified innovations and technologies are underutilized to boost rural tourism and ensure fragile village ecosystems remain intact. The study also revealed that in Himachal Pradesh, which occupies 99% of the rural area, there is very little research on rural tourism. Research suggests that principles of sustainable tourism development can lead to better rural tourism opportunities and ensure that local rural communities benefit and are protected.

Badar & Bahadure, 2020 in their case study on the city of Shimla, assessed the sustainability of tourism based on seven dimensions of sustainable tourism. These seven dimensions include tourism activities, tourism assets, tourism-related losses, tourism-related linkages, social and environmental sustainability, attractiveness and infrastructure. The case study results show that there is a significant gap between tourism potential and infrastructure development in central urban areas. Hill stations in Himachal Pradesh urgently need to implement the principles of ecotourism⁴² and aspects of sustainable tourism development. The results of the benchmark tool chosen by the authors show that despite Shimla's rich natural landscape and heritage architecture, mismanagement of natural and heritage resources has resulted in uneven distribution of tourism activity, increased air pollution, insufficient tourist activity, water shortage and traffic jams. . The study recommends revising the existing Sustainable Tourism Development Policy of 2016 to ensure better use of land and resources in tourist destinations such as Shimla, and to enable tourism to also benefit local communities.

Objective of the Study:

- To analyze the demographic profile of the tourist in Chennai
- To determine the emerging need of English language in tourist industry.

Limitations of the Study:

- The study is applicable only to the respondents.
- The results of the study are based upon the views expressed by the respondents.
- The statistical method used to analyze the data has their own limitation.
- All the limitations of primary data are applicable to this study.

Research Methodology:

- **Area of Study:** The research study was done in Chennai
- **Nature and Source of Data:** The study is based on primary data; primary data has been collected from various respondents in Chennai using questionnaire method and the secondary data have been collected from related websites, library, journals, magazines, internet and textbooks. A sample of 100 respondents were selected for the study.

- **Framework of Analysis:** Data collected from the respondents have been analyzed with the help of the following statistical tools. The statistical tools are:
 - Simple Percentage
 - Chi square Test

Table 1: Personal Profile of the Respondents

Variables	Frequency	Percent
Age (Years)		
upto25	15	15
26 to 35	48	48
36 to 45	33	33
Above 45	3	3
Gender		
Male	60	60
Female	40	40
Educational Qualification		
UG	77	77
PG	23	23
Occupation		
Agriculture	17	17
Business	34	34
Employee	25	25
Profession	24	24
Marital Status		
Unmarried	24	24
Married	76	76
Type of Family		
Joint	27	27
Nuclear	73	73
Earning Members in the Family		
One	33	33
Two	52	52
Three	15	15

Table 1 describes the demographic profile of the tourist. Out of 100 tourist who were taken for the study: it has been identified that most (60%) of the tourist are male, (48%) of the tourist age group is between 26 to 35 years, most (48%) of the tourist are under graduates, (34%) of the tourist are business people, (76%) of the tourist are married, (73%) of the tourist belong to nuclear family and (52%) of the tourist have 2 earning members in their family.

Table 2: Economic Profile of the Respondents

Monthly Income	Frequency	Percent
Up to Rs. 25000	8	8
Rs. 25001 to Rs. 50000	74	74
Above Rs. 50000	18	18
Family income		
Upto Rs. 40000	29	29
Rs. 50001 to Rs. 100000	46	46
Above Rs. 100000	25	25
Family expenditure		
Upto Rs. 25000	14	14
Rs. 25001 to Rs. 40000	37	37
Rs. 40001 to Rs. 60000	25	25
Above Rs. 60000	24	24

Table 2 describes the economic profile of the respondents. Out of 100 respondents who were taken for the study: it has been identified that most (74%) of the respondents monthly income is between Rs.25001 to Rs.50000, (46%) of the respondents family income is between Rs.50001 to Rs.100000 and (37%) of the respondents family expenditure is between Rs.25001 to Rs.40000.

Table 3: Variables and need of English language in Tourism Industry

Variables	χ^2 Value	5% level	1% level	Result
Age	9.559	12.592	16.812	NS

Gender	6.852	5.991	9.210	NS
Educational Qualification	4.672	5.991	9.210	NS
Marital Status	5.492	5.991	9.210	NS
Marital Status	5.292	5.991	9.210	NS

From the table 5, it is understood that the calculated values were lesser than the 1% and 5% level of significance and the null hypothesis is rejected. It is inferred that, on an average, tourist of different age group, gender, educational qualification and marital status does not exist any significant association between need of English language in tourism industry.

Conclusion:

In the twenty-first century, the entire world has come narrow, accessible, sharable and familiar for all the people living on this earth as English is used as a common language indeed though there are some variations in habits, societies, traditions, regions and idiosyncratic aspects. As English has got the common rates, it has been accepted as the global language among the speakers of thousands of different languages. Since wisdom and technology is progressing, there are tremendous changes taking place in the lives of the mortal beings far and wide in the world. As a result, the whole world has come a global vill and the people have to maintain good relationship with the others. Also, business, trade and commerce have come transnational and utmost of the business associations have their services in utmost of the countries. In order to maintain transnational relationship in wisdom, technology, business, education, trip, tourism and so on, English serves the purpose as a common language and a global language. It is the language substantially used not only by the scientists, business associations and the internet but also in advanced education, and tourism sectors. As English plays a dominant part in nearly all the fields in the present globalized world, there's a need to bandy its part in sightseer assiduity.

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